

Modeling COVID-19 scenarios: Experience in Taiwan

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Abstract

Control strategies to prevent the spread of COVID-19 varied across countries. In this presentation, we will present modeling studies that take into account different screening strategies, contact tracing, and severity of emerging epidemic outbreaks at different population sizes to gain insight into the dynamics of emerging infectious diseases. During the ancestral SARS-Cov-2 virus, contact tracing alone was not enough to achieve outbreak control. Although universal testing is proposed in multiple nations, its effectiveness accompanied by other measures is rarely examined. Our research investigates the necessity of universal testing when contact tracing and symptomatic screening measures are implemented. In addition, we will share our experience on modeling COVID-19 scenarios for Taiwan to steadily ease border measures.

Key Words: COVID-19, contact tracing, symptomatic screening, universal testing, ease border measures

1. Introduction

It is now widely recognized that effective pandemic prevention hinges upon a synergistic blend of key elements, including: 1) timely border sealing, 2) rigorous and comprehensive contact tracing, 3) effective quarantine and testing protocols, 4) consistent adherence to mitigation strategies, and 5) widespread acceptance and uptake of vaccination. Nevertheless, in the early stages of the pandemic, there existed a certain degree of uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of various measures, particularly the effectiveness exhibited heterogeneity across locales. Consequently, we conducted an assessment of these factors with respect to their influence on the outbreak. Our approach involved employing stochastic modelling, with a particular focus on the efficacy of contact tracing, isolation measures, and border policies. However, as a growing amount of people finished initial vaccination protocols and the booster uptake increased in 2022, we then examined the aforementioned factors on the infection spanning from 2020 to 2022 under a dynamic vaccination status using the SEIRV model. As the vaccination rate among individuals continued to rise, we subsequently undertook an analysis of the aforementioned factors in the context of infections that occurred between 2020 and 2022. This comprehensive analysis was conducted by taking into account the dynamic vaccination status using the SEIRV model.

2. Stochastic transmission model

2.1 Incubation period

The incubation period was drawn from a Weibull distribution. A corresponding serial interval for each case was then drawn from a skewed normal distribution with the mean parameter of the distribution set to the incubation period for that case, and a skew parameter chosen such that a set proportion of serial intervals was shorter than the incubation period (meaning that a set

proportion of transmission happened before symptom onset; figure 1). Our findings indicate that the Omicron variant family displayed a shorter incubation period when compared to the predominant strains observed prior to 2022. This incubation period typically ranged from 2.5 to 4.53 days, consistent with prior research.

Figure 1: The distribution of the incubation rate with a mean of 5 days.

2.2 Transmission during the incubation period

To assess the impact of transmission during the incubation period, we investigated three scenarios in which less than 1%, 15%, and 30% of transmissions, as determined by the skewed normal distribution, occurred within a 5-day incubation period.

2.3 Contact tracing

Contact tracing stands as one of the most potent strategies for mitigating transmission, especially for identifying asymptomatic individuals. Figure 2 presents a flow diagram briefly depicting its process. Circle A represents the infected but yet-to-be-captured individuals. Circles B, C and D symbolize individuals who had been exposed to the infection (A), with D being asymptomatic. Circle E represents the identified infected individuals, while Circle F represents those who have been isolated or hospitalized. In our model, we explored the probability of successful contact tracing, using values of 40%, 60%, 80%, and 90%.

Figure 2: Contact tracing process

2.4 Secondary Transmission Probability

By assuming that characterizes the association between primary and secondary outbreak cases through a negative binomial distribution, we can derive an estimation for the probability of

secondary transmission (denoted as 'p'). This estimation hinges on the parameters of the primary transmission scale ('k') and the transmissibility characteristics attributed to the variant ('r'). Figure 3 illustrates the probability distribution. Given a reproduction number of 1 and an initial case count of 10 during the primary outbreak, the resulting probability of triggering a secondary outbreak amounts 10%.

Figure 3: The probability mass function (pmf) of a negative binomial distribution with $r=1$

2.5 Simulation for stochastic transmission model

To thoroughly investigate the impact of the pandemic under varying conditions, we simulated transmission using utilizing a stochastic model with a series of parameters. The outcome indicator was the duration of the controlled period, defined as the cumulative time during which no new cases were reported within a 12 to 16-week time frame. Table 1 provides an overview of the scenarios explored. Subclinical infections denote instances of asymptomatic infection that elude detection through survey-based screening but can be discerned through molecular diagnostic techniques such as PCR or rapid antigen tests. We also investigated three tiers of isolation strategies, encompassing the isolation of symptomatic individuals, the isolation of both symptomatic and asymptomatic cases, and the isolation of all individuals who have been exposed to the infected. The incubation period for each case was stochastically derived from a Weibull distribution with a span ranging between 2.5 and 4.53. The simulation on each scenario was executed a total of 5,000 times to ensure robust statistical analysis.

Table 1: Scenarios examined with stochastic model

Scenarios	Modelled levels			
Subclinical infections	<1%	15%	30%	
Sensitivity of contact tracing	40%	60%	80%	90%
Isolation strategies	S ¹	S + A ¹	all at-risk ²	
Border-crossing undetected infections	5	20	40	
Secondary attack rate (R0)	1.5	2	2.5	

¹ S: Symptomatic, A: Asymptomatic

² All that identified by contact tracing

Figure 4a illustrates the risk associated with varying numbers of undetected infections entering the border at the onset of the simulation. With 40 initial cases, the highest among the examined scenarios, infiltrated the domestic circulation, only 32% of the simulation's duration remained under control. Whereas, the duration of the control period extended to 53.5% and 85.5% when

the initial case numbers were reduced to 20 and 5, respectively, signifying the significance of border measures and screening implementation. The sensitivity of contact tracing also plays a vital role in containing the outbreak. When 90% of the contacts were successfully traced and isolated, it resulted in the absence of a new case report for 85% of the simulation duration (Figure 4b). Conversely, under a less effective contact-tracing system, where only 40% and 60% of the contacts were identified, the proportion of time with no new cases dropped to 12% and 24%, respectively. Figure 4c shows the percentage of outbreak control at three strategies, A, B, C. The strategy A is only epidemiological investigation and isolation of symptomatic cases. The strategy B is the strategy A with testing all subclinical at-risk people and isolating positive cases. The strategy C is the strategy A with testing isolating all at-risk cases and this is a government policy for epidemic prevention in Taiwan. When only symptomatic individuals were isolated, the data revealed that a mere 3% of the duration was controlled. In contrast, when the most stringent isolation strategy was implemented, the proportion surged to 85%. Figure 4d illustrates the outcomes in response to variants with varying degrees of transmissibility. In a scenario where the reproductive number was set at 1.5, the situation remained uneventful. However, declines in the duration of control of 15% and 50% were observed when the reproductive number was elevated to 2 and 2.5, values approximately commensurate with the transmissibility of the original Wuhan strain.

Figure 4: The percentage of days under control throughout the simulation.

3. Confirmed cases and vaccination coverage in Taiwan

While the public health systems in nearly every country have been overwhelmed by SARS-CoV-2 in 2020, the situation in Taiwan, due to prompt response and a well-coordinated healthcare system, remained relatively stable. Nonetheless, this period of tranquility proved to be fleeting. The appearance and spread of both the Alpha and Delta variants underscore the tumultuous and eventful nature of the year 2021 for the Taiwanese population. Stringent measures were implemented or heightened, accompanied by recommendations for lifestyle modifications. The situation began to turn around with the introduction of vaccines. As the uptake rate steadily increased, the number of daily cases has remained consistently below 10 since the end of August. Throughout 2021, the most severe period was observed in May, with over 10 thousand infections reported within that month. In total, over the span of the 108-day pandemic,

there were more than 15,000 infections and 800 deaths.

The early success of Taiwan in the face of the pandemic has been widely credited to the implementation of prompt and adequate measures covering immediate border sealing, effective isolation and screening, well-coordinated contact tracing, and continuous promotion of maintaining social distancing and hygiene practices such as hand-washing, mask-wearing. These measures, together with the isolated geographical setting, delayed and lowered domestic circulation, thereby preventing the overload of the public health system up until the end of 2021. Nonetheless, as the Omicron emerged, its highly contagious nature not only led to a global surge in case numbers but also posed a substantial threat to the border management system in Taiwan (Figure 5). Recognizing the impracticality of completely eliminating the Omicron variant and its low mortality, the Taiwanese government reevaluated the Zero-COVID policy and explored a more sustainable and resilient framework. Consequently, aligning with global trends, restrictions began to be gradually eased in mid-2023, with the aim of balancing public health outcomes with economic livelihood and restoring pre-COVID normalcy.

Figure 5: Comparison of daily new confirmed COVID-19 cases per million people for Taiwan and other countries in 2020-2022. Source: Our World in Data. Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19).

4. Modified from original virus to Omicron

4.1 Viral dynamics of Omicron

Figure 6 illustrates the viral dynamics of Omicron. We modified from original virus to Omicron based on the research of Kucrika et al. Instead of remaining constant, the viral load exhibited changes over time from the first day of exposure to the virus. This fluctuating nature implies that the accuracy of the test is highly contingent on when the test was taken. The likelihood of a false-negative result increases as the day moves further away from day 5 to 7, which is normally when the viral load peaks. However, given each variant demonstrated distinct shedding kinetics, adjustments were made based on the epidemiological characteristics, aiming to provide the best estimation of the test accuracy possible.

Figure 6: The probability of receiving a negative RT-PCR test result given SARS-CoV-2 infection is based on the number of days since exposure. We modified from original virus to Omicron based on the research of Kucrika et al. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 173(4):262–267, August 2020.

4.2 Basic reproduction number (R0)

The basic reproduction number represents the expected number of cases directly generated by one case in a population where all individuals are susceptible to infection. In the early stages of the pandemic, the reproductive number for the original Wuhanstrain was estimated to be around 2 to 3. As new dominant variants have emerged, ongoing estimations of the reproduction number have been consistently updated. It is currently estimated that the reproduction number of Omicron BA.1 ranges from 9 to more than 30. An epidemic curve is a graph that illustrates the distribution of the onset of new cases of an infectious disease in relation to the onset of illness. Figure 7 highlights the difference in the shape of epidemic curves associated with both low (2-3) and high (10) reproductive numbers.

Figure 7: The transmission per day and corresponding R0 for Original virus and Omicron (BA.1)

4.3 Border measures during the Omicron outbreak

To determine the most effective border measures during the Omicron outbreak, we analyzed various rapid test protocols during self-health management. The effectiveness of these protocols was

quantified by assessing the reduction in cases, as compared to a scenario where no tests were administered. The study is based on the following assumptions: Firstly, all individuals arriving in Taiwan in 2022 are subject to a 14-day isolation period, consisting of a 7-day quarantine followed by a 7-day self-health management, with the day of arrival considered as Day 0. Secondly, the sensitivity of rapid tests is assumed to be 80% in comparison to the PCR tests. As demonstrated in Figure 8, rapid tests performed consecutively from day 8 to day 10 (the first 3 days of self-health management) could capture more than 90% of infected cases, outperforming any other examined scenarios. Conversely, less efficient results were observed when more tests were scheduled either closer to the end of the self-health management or dispersed throughout. Nevertheless, these scenarios remain significantly effective compared to the reference. Our findings not only highlight the necessity of sufficient rapid tests during self-health management but also provide insight into the optimal timing for their implementation.

Figure 8: The reduction rate (%) in the number of cases under different testing scenarios.

4.4 Simulation for SEIRV model

In response to the highly infectious and evolving nature of the Omicron variant, Taiwan's border policy has experienced continuous alterations since mid-2022. We conducted a simulation of the outbreak over a six-month period starting on March 2nd, 2022, utilizing the SEIRV model. Table 2 provides detailed information on the variations in vaccination coverage, efficacy, and the duration of border quarantine implemented throughout the simulation. The estimated and real epidemic curves during the Omicron stage were plotted in Figure 9. The estimation for our SEIRV model was close to the real-world data. The findings indicated that the pandemic would likely hit a peak around 1.5 months after its outbreak, with 90,000 daily infections. The pandemic would last 3 to 4 months.

Table 2: Information of days of quarantine, vaccinated coverage and vaccinated efficacy for fully vaccinated people and booster-vaccinated people

	March	April 1st - 25th	April 26th - May 1st
Days of quarantine	10	10	3, 5, 7
Vaccination			
2nd dose Coverage	77%	79%	80%
Efficacy	20%	20%	20%
Booster Coverage	43%	57%	59%
Efficacy	55%	48%	40%

Figure 9: The new case per day with new case per day in Taiwan

5. Booster coverage

In light of the emergence of new variants in early 2022, the Taiwanese government initiated a campaign to promote booster vaccinations. In order to comprehensively assess the efficacy of this promotional effort and to gain deeper insights into the dynamics of population immunity, we developed a predictive model. This model utilizes data up to May to estimate the uptake rate for the following months. The accuracy of these predictions held steady during the first two months. While the gap was widened in July and August. This underestimation can be attributed to the elevated public awareness and intensified policy promotion in response to the surge in infections (Figure 10).

Vaccination Coverage (3rd dose)

Figure 10: The predicted booster coverage percentage compared to the actual coverage from the start of 2022 through the end of August

6. Conclusion

We have conducted several modelling studies to provide policymakers timely simulations of the pandemic's progression. These simulations have empowered policymakers to efficiently formulate mitigation strategies in advance of outbreaks and conduct thorough assessments of the effectiveness of control measures. Our model, which integrates data from multi-dimensional parameters collected throughout various stages of the pandemic, our model can also reveal the associated risks it poses to different age groups.

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